

Role of Family in Work Satisfaction of Women Working in Information Technology Sector

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Abstract

The research paper delves into the pivotal role of family in influencing the work satisfaction of women employed in the Information Technology sector. It highlights the evolving societal norms and the increasing support from family members, especially spouses, in enabling women to thrive in their professional endeavours. The study reveals that a significant percentage of respondents attribute their career choices to factors like media influence, educational opportunities, and parental encouragement. Moreover, it underscores the positive correlation between family support, particularly from husbands, and the efficiency and satisfaction levels of female employees. Despite facing challenges such as role conflict and work-related stress, women in the IT industry are shown to prioritize work-life balance and derive satisfaction from both their professional and personal lives. The findings emphasize the need for continued research and initiatives to further enhance the work environment for women in the Information Technology sector.

Keywords Family, Work, Satisfaction, Women, Information, Technology, Sector.

Introduction

The new millennium ushered in an era of women occupying important positions in all positions in all fields. More and more girls are entering vocational colleges and proving themselves as excellent students and later as excellent professionals. In the last few decades, the level of education, self-confidence and more importantly, ambition has increased for women who are trying to assert their right and full place in society. Professional women who set very high standards for themselves are no exception. They changed the way they looked at themselves, and that changed the way the world looked at them.

The cause of this condition can be attributed to changes in the socio-cultural arrangement. Families have now begun to accept working women and parents have begun to explore career options for their daughters and are willing to extend their support to any extent so that they can be successful in their careers. The girls are brought up to be devoted and dedicated and have the required drive for any demanding profession they enter.

As a result, today we have women playing the role of top managers, professionals and leaders in the world of work. Organizations choose women from their rigorous selection process. They are given and take responsibility for work, tasks, roles and performance. They travel everywhere and anywhere. They attend board meetings and walk with men with their heads held high. They travel to countries and continents far and wide.

Yet a close look at women in various occupations shows that even though female labor force participation has more than doubled over the past 30-35 years, most women are still employed in a limited number of occupations. Occupational segregation is quite common. Despite the increased representation, female experts in any profession do not have equal access to different levels of the professional hierarchy. They are underrepresented in senior positions and have difficulty getting top jobs in the professions. It is true that a handful of women make it into the papers here and there, but statistically they represent a few percent of the top positions. According to Sen, women often face a greater handicap than men when it comes to employment and career advancement. He calls this

"occupational inequality", where progress to higher levels of employment and occupations is much more difficult for women than for men. (Sen, 2001).

The modernization of Indian society has not been radical and therefore traditional institutions and structures continue to exist strongly. As a result, while India promises gender equality at work, it is not accompanied by gender equality at home. Caring for family members rests primarily on women, and thus they face the dilemma of how to fulfill the expectations of career and domestic roles, leading to role conflict. Professional women are also forced to reconcile their career aspirations with societal expectations about women's behavior and family roles. Whether due to preference or lack of other options, professional women often limit their pursuit of career advancement and curtail their career aspirations for the sake of their family. Hence the present study aims to evaluate the work life balance in women employees and the challenges they face.

Objective of study

1. To examine married women role and functions at home and office.
2. To evaluate the process of managing the problems faced at both the areas.
3. To know the role of family in job satisfaction.

Review of Literature

In any research project, the purpose of introducing a proper literature review chapter is to provide empirical support for the current research work. To offer meaningful support to current research by providing literature support on a given topic. The literature review chapter also addresses theoretical issues and studies related to the issues of women working in the IT industry.

Blalack and Davis examined the measure and relationship between role ambiguity, work-related strain, and job satisfaction. Findings suggest that although the nature of the unit manager position is inherently satisfying, environmental factors contribute to high levels of role ambiguity and job strain that tend to limit job satisfaction

In her study of women in IT companies in India, Sranavanthi (2017) identified work stress as one of the significant reasons why female employees express their dissatisfaction with work. The study further suggested that practicing yoga and meditation and other physical and mental exercises can reduce stress.

In a study, G S Indumati and R Tamilselvan (2016) focus on the factors affecting the quality of work life in information technology industries. The study examined stress at work, protection and integration at work, work atmosphere, management policy and communication at work. In this study, the authors compared stress between men and women in the IT industry. The findings suggest that women face more stress at work than their male counterparts.

L Ranjit and L Mahespriya (2012) Study identified relationship between work stress and age, work stress is high in older people. The study also looked at the employee's marital status, age, qualifications and salary as factors influencing stress for workers in the IT industry. Singles have less stress at work than married people. This may be due to the family responsibilities of the spouses.

Madhavi C and Vimala B (2011), study conducted in Chennai city, 500 female employees of top IT industries are included in this study. The study identified the impact of family and workplace issues to greater stress among female employees.

Main Text

Statement of Problem

Married women in the IT sector thus face the problem of managing both home and work. To understand the level of satisfaction and factors affecting the level of satisfaction of women in the IT sector, this study is planned

From the various literature reviews narrated by the researcher, most studies focused on the performance of job satisfaction or from different and regional levels, especially urban. Since there have been rare studies on the job satisfaction of women in the information technology sector. However, the researcher focused on the female employees of the information technology sector in Bangalore Urban. With this, the researcher tried to fill the gap in the research done by the earlier scientific studies.

Significance of The Study

The study provides an insight to the challenges faced by women to maintain work life balance, so that companies can accommodate their policies and improve the work environment to facilitate women employees.

Hypothesis There is no relationship between work and family responsibilities of women in IT sector.

Methodology

Research is essentially exploratory and descriptive.

The many studies have been conducted on job satisfaction and work life balance in various fields. Literature shows a lacuna in the studies in the IT sector. Hence the study was conducted to explore and describe the various aspects related to job satisfaction and work life balance.

Geographical Area

Bangalore, the silicon city is the heart of Karnataka and the most populated city. The women in the metropolitan city are exposed to various career option and similarly various challenges are existing. Hence, it becomes the ideal sample site.

Sampling

Random sampling will be used for the following reasons:

1. The population as a whole is infinite.
2. The sample size is determined based on the statistical analysis and G Power analysis.

Composition Sample

Married women working in the information technology sector will be selected for the study. The research is limited to a sample size of 500. Due consideration will be given to the selection of married women to justify job satisfaction.

Analysis

The collected data and sample size, were subjected to statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, t-test, correlation, ANOVA were used.

Analysis of Results, discussion:

Part-A: Demographical Profile of the Respondents

Social background helps us to understand how social and cultural factors influence women in their roles, responsibilities, job satisfaction and problems they face at different stages of their lives.

i. The study found that the highest percentage of respondents in the age group of 26-30 work in information technology. At this age, they enter the profession, plan their careers, and also have the responsibilities of young wives and mothers. New young women naturally face more problems than older women with their new additional responsibilities.

ii. The study found that a maximum of 51.8 percent of respondents are urban dwellers, 26 percent of respondents fall under urban dwellers and 20.8 percent of respondents live in semi-urban areas, only 1.4 percent of respondents live in rural areas. Most of the information technology industries are established in urban centers. We see more of the urban population concentrating on the IT sector.

a. The study found that 71.8 percent of respondents belong to the GM category.

b. Being a private sector where only merit is preferred, it can be difficult for the first and second generation educated class to compete for jobs.

c. The study found that a maximum of 38.2 percent respondents are qualified in B.E/B.Tech, 19.4 percent respondents are qualified in M.Tech/M.E, 12% are diploma holders as information technology is a technical field so students with those with a technical education are preferred more.

d. The study found that more than 96.4% of professionals remain in the nuclear family. Only 3.6% remain in a joint family. This may be due to the migrant family, the cost of

living is high in urban areas, the small nuclear family is becoming the trend.

e. The study found that 65.8 percent of respondents are in love due to the influence of media, education, parental freedom in choosing life partner, etc.

PART-B: The Family

1. In the family system, the trend of 35 percent support from the husband for her career and freedom of professional life is changing. 25.6 percent of the respondents did not interfere in the family at all, they had complete freedom.

2. It is a significant positive variable that affects the efficiency of the work of female employees. From the words of K.M. In his book Marriage and Family, Kapadia sheds light on modern men towards female employees.

3. Regarding satisfaction with work in the family, 56.4 percent of respondents are satisfied with their family and 40.2 percent of respondents are very satisfied with their work. Only 3.4 percent respondents have low family satisfaction with your IT job in Bangalore city. 40.2% of respondents are very happy, 56.4% are moderate.

4. This will encourage respondents to manage their work and private lives.

5. Respondents rarely participate in family functions; 36.4 percent are unable to participate in family functions.

6. Employees of the information technology sector get a weekend holiday.

7. 73.6 percent of respondents state that their family members interfere in employment decisions. Only 26.4 percent of respondents state that their family members do not interfere in employment decisions. Individual decision-making means freedom and self-respect. Only 26.4 percent of respondents do not involve their family in employment decisions.

8. This still shows the existence of orthodox patriarchal norms for women.

9. Family support is one of the important factors for women's involvement in various work activities. Here, 49.8 percent of respondents state that they receive support from other family members. While spouse supports 29% and friends 21%, which increases employee efficiency.

10. 47.4 percent of respondents are outside working hours, have enough time for their family. 45.6 percent of respondents are outside working hours and do not have enough time for family. Only 7 percent of respondents do not answer after working hours, you have enough time for your family.

11. Women have to manage a dual role both at work and in the office. so only 47.4 percent have enough time for family.

12. 42.4 percent of respondents have occupational health problems related to muscle and joint pain, and 37.6 percent of respondents have shoulder, arm and wrist injuries due to overuse of occupational health. Only 20 percent of those surveyed have health problems related to eye strain at work

13. Health problems caused by incorrect or insufficient use of the computer or constant use of it. Health problems faced by the IT sector like vision problems, wrist pain, constant sitting leading to back pain, stomach problems, joint pain.

Hypothesis testing

There is no relationship between work and family responsibilities of women in the IT sector.

The calculated "r" value is significant at the 0.01 level of significance. The test value is less than the significant value. So the null hypothesis is accepted. It concludes that there is no significant relationship between work and family responsibilities of women in the information technology sector.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the women in the IT sector though face a lot of pressure and do feel stressed but the results are insignificant. The women have shown to be significantly satisfied with the facilities provided to them by their respective companies and hence becomes easier to maintain work life balance.

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